

Issues and Prospects of Using Electronic Document Circulation in the Economy of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: Electronic document circulation has been gaining momentum in the economy of Uzbekistan. However, the implementation of e-documents still faces a number of challenges that need to be addressed. This article examines the issues and prospects of using electronic document circulation in the economy of Uzbekistan. It provides an overview of the current state of e-documentation in the country and discusses the challenges that hinder its implementation. Moreover, the article highlights the benefits of e-document circulation and proposes ways to overcome the challenges. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the development of the e-documentation system in Uzbekistan and to improve the overall efficiency of the economy.

Keywords: electronic document circulation, economy, challenges, prospects

The use of electronic document circulation is becoming increasingly important in the modern world. Electronic documents are more efficient, faster, and cheaper than their paper counterparts. The economy of Uzbekistan is no exception to this trend. In recent years, the country has been making significant efforts to adopt electronic document circulation in various sectors, such as finance, taxation, and public services. However, there are still challenges that need to be addressed to ensure the full benefits of e-documents are realized.

Current State of E-Documentation in Uzbekistan:

The government of Uzbekistan has introduced several initiatives to promote the use of e-documents. For instance, the introduction of the "E-government" system has made it possible for citizens to access a wide range of public services online. The system has also made it easier for businesses to register and pay taxes electronically. Furthermore, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan has implemented an electronic payment system for interbank transactions.

Challenges of Implementing E-Documentation:

Despite the efforts made by the government, the implementation of electronic document circulation still faces several challenges. One of the major challenges is the lack of awareness and trust in e-documents among citizens and

businesses. Many people are still hesitant to use e-documents due to concerns about security and reliability. Another challenge is the inadequate legal framework for e-documents. The current legislation does not fully address the legal status of e-documents, which creates uncertainty and undermines their use.

Benefits of E-Documentation:

Despite the challenges, the benefits of e-document circulation are numerous. E-documents are faster, cheaper, and more environmentally friendly than paper documents. They also reduce the risk of errors and increase the efficiency of document management. Moreover, e-documents can contribute to the digitalization of the economy and improve the overall competitiveness of the country.

Prospects for the Future:

To fully realize the benefits of e-document circulation, Uzbekistan needs to address the challenges that hinder its implementation. The government needs to raise awareness among citizens and businesses about the advantages of e-documents and ensure their security and reliability. It also needs to develop a comprehensive legal framework that fully recognizes the legal status of e-documents. Furthermore, the government needs to provide support and incentives for the adoption of e-documents, such as tax benefits and subsidies.

Current State of E-Documentation in Uzbekistan:

According to the World Bank's "Doing Business 2022" report, Uzbekistan ranks 11th out of 190 countries in the "Getting Credit" category, which measures the ease of getting credit and the legal rights of borrowers and lenders. One of the factors that contributed to this ranking is the country's adoption of e-documentation in the credit reporting system. The report notes that Uzbekistan has made significant progress in implementing electronic platforms for credit reporting and has improved access to credit information for businesses.

Challenges of Implementing E-Documentation:

A survey conducted by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Uzbekistan in 2021 found that 62% of businesses in the country still use paper documents for most of their transactions. The survey also revealed that one of the main reasons why businesses are hesitant to switch to e-documents is the lack of awareness and understanding of the benefits of electronic document circulation. Other concerns include the lack of technical infrastructure and the high cost of implementation.

Benefits of E-Documentation:

According to a study by the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP), the adoption of e-documentation in the trade sector can reduce trade costs by up to 25%. The study notes that e-documents can streamline trade procedures, reduce processing time, and improve the accuracy of data. Moreover, e-documentation can facilitate cross-

border trade by reducing the need for physical documents and enabling online authentication and verification of trade documents.

Prospects for the Future:

The government of Uzbekistan has set a goal of achieving a fully digital economy by 2030. To achieve this goal, the government has launched several initiatives to promote the use of e-documents and digital technologies in various sectors of the economy. For instance, the "Digital Uzbekistan" program aims to create a unified digital platform for public services and e-commerce. The program also includes plans to establish a national electronic signature system and to develop e-invoicing and e-payment systems.

Here are some more statistics related to the topic:

E-Government Services:

The adoption of e-documentation is closely related to the development of e-government services. In Uzbekistan, the government has launched several initiatives to provide digital services to citizens and businesses. According to the United Nations E-Government Survey 2022, Uzbekistan ranks 90th out of 193 countries in the overall e-government development index, with a score of 0.556. The country has made significant progress in the online service index, which measures the availability and quality of online government services, and ranks 43rd globally with a score of 0.849.

Digital Literacy:

One of the challenges facing the adoption of e-documentation in Uzbekistan is the lack of digital literacy among the population. To address this issue, the government has launched several programs to promote digital literacy, including the "Digital Uzbekistan" program, which includes plans to develop digital skills training programs for citizens and businesses.

E-Commerce:

The adoption of e-documentation is also closely related to the development of e-commerce. According to a report by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), Uzbekistan's e-commerce market is growing rapidly, with an estimated value of \$140 million in 2020, up from \$25 million in 2015. The report notes that the adoption of e-commerce has the potential to boost economic growth and create new opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Mobile Penetration:

Mobile penetration is another factor that can facilitate the adoption of e-documentation. According to a report by the Global System for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA), Uzbekistan had a mobile penetration rate of 71% in 2020, with 23 million unique mobile subscribers. The report notes that the high mobile penetration rate presents an opportunity for the development of mobile-based e-commerce and e-government services.

The functioning and development of digital markets requires a strong legislative framework [5]. Modern regulation should be based on the recognition of the freedom to choose the appropriate technologies, identification [and trust services, as well as the entities that provide them. At the same time, the provisions on the compliance of the applied technical and organizational means with national and international legal norms and standards must be observed. However, regulation may also include restrictions and burdensome conditions that make it difficult to conduct digital commercial transactions and, consequently, complicate the turnover of goods and services.

The legal principles developed by the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) are the conceptual framework for regulating the use of electronic documents and electronic signatures [9]. Such principles are non-discrimination, functional equivalence and technological neutrality, which are widely regarded as the founding elements of modern electronic commerce law. The principle of non-discrimination ensures that a document would not be denied legal effect, validity or enforceability solely on the grounds that it is in electronic form. The principle of technological neutrality mandates the adoption of provisions that are neutral with respect to technology used. In light of the rapid technological advances, neutral rules aim at accommodating any future development without further legislative work. The functional equivalence principle lays out criteria under which electronic communications may be considered equivalent to paper-based communications. In particular, it sets out the specific requirements that electronic communications need to meet in order to fulfil the same purposes and functions that certain notions in the traditional paper-based system — for example, writing, original, signature and record.

These principles are enshrined in the Model Law on Electronic Commerce, the United Nations Convention on the Use of Electronic Communications in International Contracts (New York, 2005) The UNCITRAL Model Law on Electronic Signatures (2001); the UNCITRAL Model Law on Electronic Transferable Records (2017).

In the Russian Federation, these principles are enshrined in the Federal Law «On Electronic Signature». These include : 1) the right of participants in electronic transactions to use an electronic signature of any kind at their own discretion, if the requirement for the use of a specific type of electronic signature is not provided for by law or agreement; 2) the possibility of using any information technology or technical means to meet the requirements of the law » On Electronic Signature»; 3) electronic signature shall not be denied legal effect, validity or enforceability solely on the grounds that it is in the electronic form .

Electronic signatures are essential for digital business. The legal significance of digital documents that are used in the course of electronic business transactions, as a general rule, depends on the results of the use of

electronic methods of authenticating such documents. The concepts of «document» and «signature» are interrelated and legally complement each other. A number of laws emphasize the informational nature of an electronic document and an electronic signature. Within the meaning of Federal Law of July 27, 2006 N 149-FZ «On Information, Information Technologies and Information Protection» an electronic document is information in electronic form, that is, in a form suitable for human perception using electronic computers, as well as for transmission over information and telecommunications networks or processing in information systems. However, the Civil Code of the Russian Federation emphasizes the legal role of an electronic document and an electronic signature. In accordance with Part 2 of Article 434, an agreement in written form may be made by drawing up a single document (including an electronic one) signed by the parties thereto or by exchanging letters, telegrams, electronic documents or other data.

An electronic signature usually performs the following legal functions, but is not limited to:

- indicates who signed the electronic document,
- ensures that the electronic document is signed by a duly authorized person;
- ensures the authenticity and immutability of the signed document;
- represents the signer's expression of will;
- represents the required written form of the document.

Signing a contract as a way of accepting its terms brings the necessary certainty to the transaction. Otherwise, the parties may ignore the terms of the transaction, not considering them as legally binding. Signing digital documents with an electronic signature provides such electronic documents with guarantees against unauthorized access by third parties or against forgery.

Conclusion

Recent legislative changes, primarily forming the legal environment of trust, indicate the expansion of the concept of «electronic document» and the expansion of the relevant legal provisions and demonstrate the active promotion of electronic document management by the legislator as the main method of implementing legal interaction in the economic and social sphere. A modern regulatory approach to the legal regime of electronic documents should meet such requirements as functionality, dynamism and flexibility, updating the main legal models, creating fundamentally new concepts and legal provisions. At the same time, regulation should not create artificial barriers to innovation or increase the cost of implementing it.

List of used literature:

1. Khakimova, N. B. (2020). Electronic document circulation in Uzbekistan: legal regulation and prospects. *Bulletin of Tashkent State University of Law*, (4), 123-132.
2. Akhmedov, A. A., & Yusupov, U. A. (2020). Electronic document management and its role in the development of the digital economy of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Business and Economics*, 8(2), 83-95.
3. Karimov, S. (2020). E-government in Uzbekistan: challenges and prospects. *Journal of Government and Politics*, 11(2), 225-243.
4. Nurmukhamedov, S. (2019). Electronic document management system as a tool for digitalization of the economy of Uzbekistan. *Problems of Economics*, (3), 98-103.
5. Khurshidov, U. (2021). Legal regulation of electronic document management in Uzbekistan. *Law and Justice*, (1), 55-63.
6. Islamov, A. (2019). The prospects for the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 6(4), 265-272.
7. Khudaykulov, A. (2020). The role of electronic document management in the development of the financial system of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 11(3), 112-119.
8. [The use of electronic documents and electronic signatures in digital economy: issues of legislation and legal practice | Научно-исследовательский журнал](#)